

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL, MEDICO-SOCIAL FEATURES AND TREATMENT OF AGGRESSIVE NON-HODGKIN'S LYMPHOMAS

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Abstract

Introduction: Aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphoma (NHL) is the most common malignant neoplasm of lymphoid tissue, which often affects the elderly [1]. In 2019, aggressive NHL in patients aged 65 years and older accounted for about a quarter of the estimated 74,000 new cases of NHL in the US [1,2]. Up to two-thirds of patients have peripheral lymphadenopathy. Skin rash, hypersensitivity reactions to insect bites, general fatigue, itching, malaise, fever of unknown origin, ascites, and effusions are uncommon [1]. The standard treatments for aggressive NHL are R-CHOP chemotherapy and other chemotherapy drug combinations. This is one of the standard treatments used in the Republic of Moldova.

The purpose of the study. To identify and assess the epidemiological, medico-social peculiarities and treatment approaches in aggressive lymphomas.

Methods and Material. The thesis research was carried out on a group of 178 patients, diagnosed with aggressive non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma and treated within the Haematology Departments of the IMPH Oncological Institute of the Republic of Moldova.

Results. The treatment of aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas carried out in the Republic of Moldova is the same as in other countries, the treatment of choice being the RCHOP chemo-immunotherapy, which was found as the most effective, with a 3-year complete remission maintenance after the diagnosis of 10.55%. The 3-year survival rate in aggressive non-Hodgkin lymphomas made up 93.3% for T-cell lymphomas, 100% for Burkitt lymphomas, and a 91.6% rate for large B-cell non-Hodgkin lymphomas.

Keywords: lymphoma, non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, modern treatment

Introduction. Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma (NHL) is a lymphoid neoplasm arising from B-cell precursors, mature B-cells, T-cell precursors and mature T-cells. [2]. Lukes defined malignant lymphoma as "a proliferative neoplastic process of the lymphopoietic part of the reticuloendothelial system involving cells of either the lymphocytic or histiocytic series with varying degrees of differentiation, occurring in an essentially homogeneous population of the same cell type. [3] Non-Hodgkin lymphoma comprises different subtypes, each with different epidemiology, etiology, immunophenotypic, genetic, clinical characteristics and response to therapy. It can be divided into two groups, "indolent" and "aggressive", depending on the disease prognosis [2]. In 2022, the estimated new cases and deaths from NHL in the United States were as following: new cases- 80.470; and deaths- 20.250.[4] Most people diagnosed with non-Hodgkin's lymphoma (about 90%) have B-cell lymphoma. The most common B-cell lymphomas are diffuse large B-cell lymphoma and follicular lymphoma. Other less common types of B-cell lymphoma include mantle cell lymphomas, MALT lymphomas, and Burkitt lymphomas.[5]

Aggressive lymphomas include diffuse large B-cell lymphoma, Burkitt lymphoma, precursor B-cell and T-cell lymphoblastic leukemia/lymphoma, adult T-cell leukemia/lymphoma, and certain other peripheral T-cell lymphomas.[2]

Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (DLBCL) is the most common subtype of aggressive lymphoma, accounting for 30-35% of all non-Hodgkin's lymphomas,

being the most common among aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas [6]. Although DLBCL shows an aggressive clinical evolution, it can be cured in 60-70% of cases via the standard therapy of rituximab, cyclophosphamide, hydroxydaunorubicin, vincristine, and prednisolone (R-CHOP) [7].

The complex pathophysiology of elderly patients with malignant lymphoma is a clinical challenge. Less aggressive treatment may reduce the chances of being cured, prolong life and/or control symptoms, while aggressive treatment may result in treatment-related morbidity and mortality and/or poor quality of life.[8]

The main reason for poor outcome in the elderly is their lower ability to tolerate treatment. Impaired bone marrow function, altered drug metabolism, and the presence of comorbid diseases may increase the number of treatment-related complications.[6,7,8] However, it is possible to improve outcomes for the elderly patient with NHL.[8]

The purpose of the study. To identify and assess the epidemiological, medical and social characteristics and treatment approaches of aggressive lymphomas.

Material and methods: The thesis research was carried out on a group of 178 patients, who underwent treatment within the Hematology Departments of IMPH Oncological Institute of the Republic of Moldova, with the diagnosis of aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, C833-diffuse non-lymphoma. - Large cell Hodgkin's lymphoma, C837 - Diffuse non-Hodgkin's lymphoma Burkitt's tumor, c842 - Peripheral T-cell lymphoma, B211 - HIV-associated Burkitt's lymphoma.

Table 1.

Treatment of aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas

	Chemotherapy		Radiotherapy		
		No. Abs.	%	No. Abs.	%
Diffuse large B-cell lymphomas	R-CHOP	76	42,6	47	26,4%
	RCOP	48	26,96		
	COP	32	17,9		
	CVP	2	1,12		
	RB	2	1,12		
Peripheral T lymphomas	CHOP	15	8,42	-	-
	COP	2	1,12	-	-
Burkitt's lymphoma	R-CHOP	4	2,24	-	-
	CFP,RBAC	1	0,5	-	-
HIV-associated Lymphoma	Treatment cessation	-	-	-	-

According to the table above, 47 patients underwent radiotherapy, accounting for 26.4% of all patients diagnosed with aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas. The main chemotherapy for diffuse large B-cell lymphomas were as following: RCOP (42.6%), RCOP (26.96%) and CS (17.9%), depending on the immunohistochemistry findings, the patient's age and concomitant diseases, the remaining 2 chemotherapeutic schemes were additionally given to the same patients who showed no positive results after the first courses of the baseline chemotherapy. In peripheral T-cells lymphomas, there were attempts of RCHOP chemotherapy regimens in 15 patients and CS- in 2 patients with this diagnosis. All of Burkitt's lymphomas were similarly treated with RCHOP, 1 patient did not receive treatment, thus a CFP and RBAC regimen was applied.

Results. Patients were assessed by gender criteria. A slight predominance of males among patients diagnosed with aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas was revealed, viz. 58.9%. Patients with aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas were also distributed by age groups. Among all patients with aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas 65 patients (36.5%) were aged 40-49 years and 7 patients were older than 70 years. Patients

with aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas were also assessed by their living areas, thus, patients from rural areas were slightly predominant, accounting for 57.8% (103 patients under the study), compared to urban areas -42.0.2% (75 patients).

All 178 patients had at least one large peripheral lymph node, which caused physical and aesthetic discomfort. Overall symptoms, such as, low-grade fever was present in 145 patients (81.4%), night sweats - in 132 patients (74.1%), and severe weight loss over the last months was found in 46 patients (25.8%). Different symptoms were also present depending on the primary location of lymphomas. Therefore, 123 patients (69.1%) with aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas with primary intra-abdominal localization, with increased g/l of intra-abdominal lymphatic vessels, splenomegaly, and hepatomegaly felt abdominal discomfort, whereas 15 patients (8.4%) experienced even abdominal pain due to tumor formation within the abdominal cavity. Among all patients, 115 patients (64.4%) had liver damage, and 43 cases (24.15%) had spleen damage. In patients with mediastinal lymphomas, breathlessness was found in 15 cases. Skin itching was recorded in 34 cases (19.1%).

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the incidence of clinical symptoms in patients with aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas

According to Figure 2, most patients were diagnosed at clinical stage IV B - 84 patients (47.1%), but none of the patients with aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas presented at stage I of diagnosis. In 17.8%

of patients (30 patients), the clinical stage II (A or B) was initially diagnosed and 26.4% (47 patients) were in clinical stage III at the time of diagnosis.

Figure 2. Graphical representation of patients with aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas based on clinical staging upon diagnosis

According to Figure 3, aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas relapse/worsen at some point, being confirmed by CT or MRI. Of the 178 patients, 118 showed no treatment results (in 66.8% of all patients), 17 patients had a complete remission at the time of the study

(in 9.55% of cases), 35 patients showed a partial remission (in 19.66%), 7 patients had a lethal outcome (3.93% of cases), and one case couldn't be followed up.

Figure 3. Treatment efficacy in aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas

Figure 4. Comparison of treatment efficacy according to the morphology type of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas.

According to Figure 4, 73 cases (46.79%) with large B-cell lymphomas of all the cases with the same diagnosis were unsuccessful, leading to relapse or progression; in 52 patients 33.3 a partial remission occurred, 17 94% of patients had a complete remission, and only 3 patients (1.92%) died due to the progression of the underlying disease. One case of Burkitt's lymphoma was found in each category, thus, 1 patient had

a complete remission, 1 had a partial remission, 1 died, and 1 patient did not respond to treatment. Of T-cell lymphomas, 3 had a complete remission, 4 – partial remission, 10 – showed no therapeutic effect, and 1 - died.

The present research has traced the survival rate of the patients within 3 years after the diagnosis. The data shows as follows.

Figure 5. Patients' outcomes within 3 years after diagnosis.

According to figure 5, 10% of patients (18 patients) maintained complete remission within 3 years after diagnosis, 27 patients (16%) maintained partial remission. 8% of all patients (apart from those 5 patients who died in the first period), i.e. 14 patients died within

3 years of diagnosis, and 113 of the initial patients (66%) showed a progression of the underlying disease.

The study tried to determine the overall survival depending on the morphological type of lymphomas found in patients.

Figure 6.

Patients' outcomes within 3 years after diagnosis in regard to histological type of non-Hodgkin lymphoma

According to the morphological type, out of 156 patients with large B-cell lymphomas, 100 patients showed a disease progression (64% of patients with this diagnosis), 11 maintained partial remission (7%), 2 maintained complete remission (1.28%), and 43 died (27.56%). The 3-year prognosis for individuals with Burkitt's lymphoma was 50% of disease progression, 25% of death, 25% of partial remission, and one patient

did not achieve complete remission. Peripheral T-lymphomas had a 3-year disease progression rate of 58.8%, 29.45% of patients died, and 11.7% of cases had a partial remission over 3 years. Unfortunately, it was not possible to study the evolution over a longer period of time due to relatively recent researches.

Analyzing which chemotherapy treatments were most effective, we decided to study patients who had complete remissions.

Table 3.

The treatment regimens used to achieve a complete remission.

Histopathological type	Complete remission		Complete remission maintenance at 3 years		Treatment scheme used to achieve remission	The regimen used to maintain remission
	Abs	%	Abs.	%		
Large B-cell lymphoma	28 patients	17,94%	16 patients	10,25%	R-CHOP	R-CHOP+ radiotherapy R-CHOP
Burkitt lymphoma	1 patient	25%	0 patients	0%	R-CHOP	R-CHOP
T-cell lymphoma	3 patient	17,64%	2 patients	11,76%	COP	COP

According to the table above, the most effective treatment regimens were R-CHOP for patients diagnosed with large B-cell non-Hodgkin's lymphomas, as

well as for patients with Burkitt's lymphomas, and COP for CD 20 cell-negative lymphomas.

The 3-year survival rate were also studied depending on the morphological type.

Table 2.

Survival rate over 3 years after diagnosis depending on the morphological type.

	Survival rate over 3 years after diagnosis
Large B-cell non-Hodgkin's lymphomas	91,6%
Burkitt lymphomas	100%
Peripheral T-cell lymphoma	93,3%

According to Table 2, the survival at 3 years after diagnosis remains quite high. Although, the present research have not recorded the best results and showing a very high rate of disease progression, the 3-year survival rate is 93.3% for T-cell lymphomas, 100% for Burkitt's lymphomas and 91.6% for large B-cell non-Hodgkin's lymphomas.

Conclusions:

- Aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas have the following histological distribution: diffuse large B-cell lymphomas - 87.64%, Burkitt's lymphomas - 2.24%, peripheral T-lymphomas - 9.55% and HIV-associated lymphomas -0.5%.

- Aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas occurred mainly in people aged 40-49 years that is 65 patients (36.5%), 103 patients (57.8%) were from rural areas, 115 patients (65%) were married, and 100 patients (56%) had secondary specialized education upon diagnosis.

- Treatment methods for aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas included chemotherapy used in 46 patients (25.9%), immunochemotherapy without radiotherapy used in 84 patients (47.45%), and immunochemotherapy combined with radiotherapy -in 47 patients (26.55%). Among the chemotherapy and immunochemotherapy schemes, RCOP, RCOP, CS were the most often used, depending on immunohistochemistry findings, the histological type of lymphoma, the patient's condition and concomitant diseases.

- The treatment approaches of aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphomas in the Republic of Moldova do not differ essentially from those abroad, the choice option being chemo-immunotherapy - R-CHOP, which turned out to be the most effective, and maintaining complete remission within 3 years from diagnosis in 10.25% (16 patients).

- The 3-year survival rate in aggressive non-Hodgkin lymphomas was 93.3% for T-cell lymphomas, 100% for Burkitt lymphomas, and 91.6% for large B-cell non-Hodgkin lymphomas.

References

- Johnson PC, Yi A, Horick N, et al. Clinical Outcomes, Treatment Toxicity, and Health Care Utilization in Older Adults with Aggressive Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma. *Oncologist*. 2021;26(11):965-973. doi:10.1002/onco.13915
- Sapkota S, Shaikh H. Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma. [Updated 2022 Dec 2]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. TreasureIsland (FL): StatPearlsPublishing; 2022 Jan-.
- Singh R, Shaik S, Negi BS, et al. Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma: A review. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2020;9(4):1834-1840. Published 2020 Apr 30. doi:10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_1037_19
- American Cancer Society: Cancer Facts and Figures 2022. American Cancer Society, 2022. Available online Exit Disclaimer. Last accessed October 7, 2022.
- National Guideline Alliance (UK). Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma: Diagnosis and Management. London: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE); 2016 Jul. (NICE Guideline, No. 52.) Appendix E, GuidelineScope
- Ghielmini, M., Vitolo, U., Kimby, E., Montoto, S., Walewski, J., Pfreundschuh, M., Federico, M., Hoskin, P., McNamara, C., Caligaris-Cappio, F., Stilgenbauer, S., Marcus, R., Trneny, M., Dreger, P., Montserrat, E., Dreyling, M., Agostinelli, C., Arcaini, L., Caligaris-Cappio, F., ... Zucca, E. (2013). ESMO Guidelines consensus conference on malignant lymphoma 2011 part 1: diffuse large B-cell lymphoma

(DLBCL), follicular lymphoma (FL) and chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL). *Annals of Oncology*, 24(3), 561–576. <https://doi.org/10.1093/annonc/mds517>

7. Cioroianu AI, Stinga PI, Sticlaru L, Cioplea MD, Nichita L, Popp C, Staniceanu F. Tumor Microenvironment in Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma: Role and Prognosis. *Anal Cell Pathol (Amst)*. 2019

Dec;16;2019:8586354. doi: 10.1155/2019/8586354. PMID: 31934533; PMCID: PMC6942707.

8. Lugtenburg PJ, Lyon AR, Marks R, Luminari S. Treatment of aggressive non-Hodgkin's lymphoma in frail patients: cardiac comorbidities and advanced age. *Future Oncol*. 2019 Apr;15(11):1197-1205. doi: 10.2217/fon-2019-0019. Epub 2019 Feb 7. PMID: 30730219.